

LEARNING TOGETHER EACH OTHER'S LANGUAGE

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Since officially September this year, I have lived here in Toshkent. My wife is Uzbek, we live with her mom and our cat, Miya, in a neighbourhood considered as being part of the centre. I have taught French at the Alliance Française since last Spring, and I work at Profi University since mid-October, as Deputy Head of the Tourism Department. Behind this bombastic title, my occupation consists in acting as an Academic Coordinator to ensure that the double degree programme we are developing with a French higher school of tourism is compliant with our mutual commitments and the regulations to which we are subject, as well as to advice and accompany students regarding the exchange year some of them will accomplish in their fourth academic year.

Before September, I had come several times to Uzbekistan. The very first one was in November 2018, a week, Buxoro – Samarqand – Toshkent. Through an online accommodation platform, I was invited to have plov at a local family's. At the end of the dinner, I was warmly invited to come back to your country, which I did a few months later, in April 2019. The daughter of the house and I confessed our mutual feelings. But it is not before last year that I came back to Uzbekistan and we married only this year, in Spring. The pandemic has passed by, as well as episodes of our complicated lives. Adversity at a global and personal scale made us stronger and made our love grow. And after all we have been through, we are now married and living together here. As a binational and bicultural couple, it is, if not natural, logical that we start learning each other's language.

To be honest, it would be fairer if, instead of me, my wife was here this morning to tell you this story, since she is much more gifted in languages than I am. As she is having family obligations and she trusts me to tell you about our mutual apprenticeship, I will do my best. Above all, we come from different linguistic backgrounds. She is Uzbek. She was born at the very end of the Soviet Union but the main language spoken at the family table was Russian. Uzbek is her mother language, but she knows Russian even better. Since her mother is an English teacher, my wife also has an excellent level in this language, which is the one we mostly use to communicate together. I am French, and though I have lived in seven countries before coming here, I can only speak, besides my mother language, a passable English and a slightly more convincing Italian, with a proficiency in the latter two languages equal to a C1 level. My wife's English, as her mother's and as the English of many Uzbek speakers, is influenced by American English, while mine is clearly more imbued with the European roots of Dusty Springfield's language.

For historical reasons dating back to the conquest by William of Normandy, English is made of 29% words of French origin¹ and an additional 29% words of Latin or other romance languages' roots, which makes it easier for me – I studied Latin in middle school – to make it mine. It is apparently not the case for the vast majority of my fellow citizens, whose reputation for being reluctant to speak English is well established. In 2023, French people were the 43rd in the world in terms of English proficiency², on a par with Cuba, and well behind Benelux, Nordics, German-speaking, Baltic countries, but also Croatia, Greece, Poland, Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia, Serbia, Czechia, Moldova, Albania, and all the European romance language countries, namely Portugal, Romania, Italy and Spain. Are we that bad at English and foreign languages? Or are we just reluctant to speak the nowadays uncontested *lingua franca mundi*, a status once ours? Could it be jealousy?

1 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_English_words_of_French_origin

2 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/EF_English_Proficiency_Index (to be taken cautiously)

In a globalized world, to feel like a fish in the water, knowing English is mandatory. So why bother learning other languages? Why did I learn Italian, starting at middle school? Most of French pupils have the choice between only German and Spanish as a second foreign language but, being in a region bordering Italy, I had the possibility to choose Italian. I remember I was offered to learn German, as I had good grades and German is considered difficult, attracting best students regardless of their interest for the language and its cultures (with an “s” because, across time, Germany and Austria have developed specific and different cultures within the European civilization). Spanish? I never considered this option. Spanish came later: it is easy to read and its rules are less tricky than the French language’s. My mother briefly lived in Rome in her young age, her family had friends in Turin, a few hours drive from home, and we spent a lot of Sundays there when I was a child. But I mostly remember I insisted then on the ease of learning Italian, even saying it would save me a lot of painful working hours – I was lazy and proud of it. I was 12, and I had the right to be lazy. If later I happened to briefly regret not to have learnt German (after falling in love with Wien), I never regretted being lazy, because not only Italian is very easy for a French speaker, but it is also unspeakably (and subjectively) beautiful, and its melody reflects in the opera as well as in the *musica leggera – dalla Scala a San Remo*, and the country, with its mountains, monuments, coasts, shows an unequalled variety of landscapes, climates and terroirs. Italian is for my *piacere e felicità*. If English is mandatory, Italian, for me, is necessary.

My wife learnt Russian, which was spoken at home along with Uzbek. She also learnt English at school, and took advantage of her mother’s profession as an English teacher. Since October, she has been learning French at the Alliance Française, where I teach two days a week. And I have started learning Russian, as the Alliance Française provides its native French teachers with such courses. Why not Uzbek, which is the only official language of the country? The language policy of Uzbekistan not being the topic here, I will leave it aside and might keep it for another statement, when I know better about this really fascinating subject.

My wife is learning French as a beginner, at an A1 level, twice two hours a week, with an Uzbek teacher trained to teach to beginners. Being a French teacher, and a native, I do not consider myself, for the moment, ready to teach to beginners, because it requires pedagogic skills I do not have now. This is why I rejected several offers to teach French to beginners, and I am convinced that, native or not, teaching to beginners is a very serious thing and my Uzbek colleagues, at the Alliance Française or at Profi University, do it much better than I would. But when we review the lessons with my wife, with the notebook and the notes she takes, it is inspiring, and I can measure how accurate is the notebook, how good is the teacher and how outstanding is the student.

The Russian lessons I take are given by a fellow teacher of the Alliance Française, who is an Uzbek woman speaking fluent Russian and being very nice, understanding and patient. The material we use is unfortunately not as great as the material given to my wife and her fellow students. And my hectic professional rhythm does not always make it possible for me to attend the lessons. So my wife is much more advanced in French than I am in Russian, and it would be quite easier for now to have a conversation together in French than in Russian. However, we had the idea to use the notes taken during her courses to enhance my Russian vocabulary. She would show me what she did, and I would apply the notions and vocabulary she learnt to Russian. It would produce a booklet with words in French, Russian and even Uzbek, loosely based on the Guide parlé français-ouzbek-russe that she found at home and gave me. A precious resource.

Another idea, quite conventional at first sight, would be to take note of everything that is in our environment, starting with home. From the front door of the apartment, we would list every item from the floor to the ceiling, and name them in French, Russian and Uzbek (FRUZ). We would also list every item in the furniture, here mostly a big wardrobe and cupboard, where we store, among other things, Miya's food. We would then apply the same method to the other rooms.

In the hallway for example, there is a doormat, a plate for Miya, a water fountain for Miya, a shoe rack, a wardrobe, a bench, a coffee table, two frames on the wall, various commuturs. В коридоре, например, есть коврик, посуда для Мии, фонтанчик для воды для Мии, полка для обуви, шкаф, скамейка, журнальный столик, две рамки на стене, различные выключатели. Masalan, koridorda gilam, Miya uchun plastinka, Miya uchun suv favvorasi, poyabzal uchun javon, shkaf, skameyka, kofe stoli, devordagi ikkita ramka, turli xil kalitlar mavjud. Now we have a few weeks each of learning the other's language, we feel a bit more confident and mind you this statement, this morning, in front of you, may act as a motivating element to implement what I have just described.

For this reason, and also because I was in another life a journalist, and I am now working in Toshkent in the higher education, I would like to thank the Ministry of Higher Education, Sciences and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan, for letting me today share a bit of my experience in your country, a country for which, as for my wife, my love is growing everyday. Sizga katta rahmat!

